

Tebuconazole Analytics for OECD Test 239 with *Myriophyllum spicatum*

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Analysis of tebuconazole

Tebuconazole were measured at the start and end (day 14) of the test in Smart and Barko medium in each treatment and controls. Samples for TBZ analysis were concentrated and purified using SPE (Strata XL, Phenomenex) and then 1 µl of the extract was analyzed using a 7890B GC system (Agilent) coupled to a 7010B triple-quadrupole mass spectrometer with HES ion source (Agilent). To ensure the accuracy of the method, blank samples were spiked with the internal standard TBZ-D6. The samples were separated using an OPTIMA 35 MS column (30 m x 0.25 mm, 0.25 µm) at constant flow (1.5 mL/min helium). Electron impact ionization in MRM mode was used for detection and quantification (TBZ: m/z 250 → 125 and m/z 252 → 127; TBZ-D6: m/z 258 → 127).

The limit of detection (LOD) was 0.15 µg/L and the limit of quantification (LOQ) was 0.5 µg/L TBZ for water.

Results

Table 1: Measured Tebuconazole values in medium for the OECD test 239

Treatment nominal concentrations [µg/L]	Mean day 0	Mean day 0	Mean day 14	Mean day14
	Smart & Barko medium			
	Repeat determination	Repeat determination	Repeat determination	Repeat determination
	[µg/L]	[%]	[µg/L]	[%]
Control	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
25	25.2	101	19.4	77.6
50	46.5	92.9	41.4	82.8
100	84.6	84.6	86.3	86.3
200	202	101	160	80.1
400	386	96.5	333	83.2
800	754	94.2	645	80.6

Calibration Details

Sample No	Accuracy	Accuracy	Accuracy MW	Final Conc.	Final Conc.	Conc. MW	Residues [%]
	[%]	[%]		[ng/ml]	[ng/ml]		
	1. Injektion	2. Injektion		2. Injektion	3. Injektion		
KAL_TEB_472_0,75	107	119	113	0.802	0.895	0.848	13.1
KAL_TEB_472_1,5	100	100	100	1.50	1.49	1.50	0.248
KAL_TEB_472_2,5	97.3	98.6	97.9	2.43	2.47	2.45	2.07
KAL_TEB_472_10	99.4	98.3	98.8	9.94	9.83	9.88	1.18
KAL_TEB_472_25	96.6	95.4	96.0	24.1	23.9	24.0	3.99
KAL_TEB_472_50	94.1	93.6	93.8	47.0	46.8	46.9	6.16
KAL_TEB_472_100	98.2	98.9	98.5	98.2	99	98.5	1.46
KAL_TEB_472_250	101	101	101	252	252	252	0.732
KAL_TEB_472_300	101	102	101	302	306	304	1.26